

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FOREIGN LANGUAGE ANXIETY AND LANGUAGE LEARNING STRATEGIES IN LEARNING ARABIC AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

Muhammad Hasan^{1*}

¹Master of Arabic Language Education, Faculty of Education, University of Malaya,
Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

*Corresponding author: hasanmuhammad297@siswa.um.edu.my

Abstract

The objective of this study was to decide the levels of foreign language anxiety (FLA) and the frequency of language learning strategies (LLS) among university students studying arabic courses in Maulana Malik Ibrahim Islamic State University Malang, Indonesia. This study was also to investigate the correlation between the levels of students' FLA and their frequency in using LLS. The instruments used in this study consist of Horwitz and Cope's Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) and Oxford's Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL). The participants of the study were 108 students selected based on convenience sampling method. Regarding the descriptive statistics, the results illustrated that the overall participants had average levels of anxiety and female students were indicated to be a little more anxious compared to male students. In terms of LLS, the results pointed out that overall strategy categories fall in medium level except compensation strategies. For the entire sample, the results of Pearson product-moment correlation revealed that there was a statistically significant negative correlation ($r = -.190$) between FLA and LLS. This correlation means that the higher use of language learning strategies is correlated to less amount of Foreign Language Anxiety in learning Arabic.

DOI : [10.5281/zenodo.2540583](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2540583)

1. Introduction

Generally speaking, anxiety is defined as the tension subjective feelings, apprehension, and worry linked with the arousal of the automatic nervous system [1]. Similarly, MacIntyre and Gardner demonstrated language anxiety is the feeling of tension and apprehension particularly related to the contexts of second language, such as speaking, listening, and learning [2]. Ellis argued that "foreign language anxiety is a type of situation-specific anxiety associated with attempts to learn a second language and communicate in it" [3]. Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope gave a definition of Language Anxiety as "a distinct complex of self-perceptions, beliefs, feelings, and behaviors related to classroom language learning arising from the uniqueness of the foreign language learning process." [4]. Many researchers said that anxiety influences language performance [5], language learning [6] [3] [7], motivation level of performance and attitude in learning a specific topic [8]. Wilson describes that the higher levels of foreign language anxiety of learners, the lower mark they gained on exam [9]. In addition, Effiong adds that language learners would feel nervous when they speak nearby natives and feel uncomfortable and not confident to speak in foreign language classroom [10]. Foreign language anxiety is different from general communication anxiety, foreign language anxiety is a separate and distinct phenomenon particular to language learning. However, foreign language anxiety and general communication anxiety share certain characteristics, including fear of doing mistakes, a desire to be perfect when speaking. Based on the nature of foreign language anxiety has been traditionally classified into

trait anxiety, situational anxiety, and state anxiety [1]. On the other hand, anxiety characteristics can be identified on a from continuum from stability to transience with trait anxiety correlated to a stable predisposition to be nervous in a wide range of situation [1]. As reported that students commonly experience foreign language anxiety in testing situation [4].

In context of learning foreign language, strategies are playing an essential role in outcomes of learning process [2]. Oxford stated that language learning strategies are specific action, behaviours, steps, or techniques such as looking for conversation partners, or giving encouragement to deal with a difficult task applied by students to improve their learning [11]. In addition to this, language learning strategies are tools for active and self-directed involvement in the improvement of communication ability [1]. The use of suitable strategies in learning foreign language is also considered to be able in enhancing proficiency and self-confidence in many context [12] [13]. In terms of lowering the levels of foreign language anxiety, One of the most factors considered to overcome this issue is language learning strategies. As reported by Shabani that the use of language learning strategies is correlated to less amount of foreign language anxiety in Iranian university students context [1]. He added that those students who used more strategies tend to have lower levels of anxiety compared to they who used less. Lucas et. al explained that foreign language learners use strategies not only to learn the target language but also to solve their foreign language anxiety [14]. Similarly, Mohammadi et al stated that high language learning strategies users had a relatively lower foreign language anxiety level than low language learning strategies users [15]. Noormohammadi also reported that language learning strategies can affect the level of foreign language anxiety [15]. Specifically, the use of affective learning strategies may reduce the level of foreign language anxiety [16].

2. Statement of Problem

As explained above, foreign language anxiety is common phenomenon among learners studying any foreign language. Learners often become anxious or nervous in learning or using the target language. Consequently, anxiety may affects their outcomes of learning process. Thus, this issue is essential to be able to identify those students who are specifically anxious in learning foreign language.

One of the most important factors may lower the levels of foreign language anxiety is language learning strategies. Many studies have been conducted in this area. Nevertheless, just few research have investigated the correlation between foreign language anxiety and the use of language learning strategies among university students taking arabic courses.

Therefore, this present research is to explore the relationship between language anxiety in learning arabic as a foreign language and the use of language learning strategies among students of Maulana Malik Ibrahim Islamic State University.

3. Research Questions

- 1) What levels of anxiety are present among university students in learning Arabic?
- 2) What types of language learning strategies do university students use in learning Arabic?
- 3) Is there any significant relationship between foreign language anxiety and language learning strategies among university students students in learning Arabic?

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Research Design

Since this study is quantitative research, Survey research design was used to accomplish. It is to determine the factors that may cause anxiety in Arabic learning as a foreign language and language learning strategies used by students of Islamic State University Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia.

4.2 Data Collection Instrument

This present research used two questionnaires in collecting the data. For collecting the data of foreign language anxiety, the questionnaire of Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety scale (FLCAS) designed by Horwitz et al is used and then converted into Arabic learning context as the questionnaire [4]. This questionnaire of FLCAS contains 33 items that are classified by the factors causing anxiety in learning foreign language. The causes are identified as communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety, and anxiety in Classroom. These are detailed classification of the questionnaire items:

Table 1. Numbers of items in foreign language anxiety questionnaire

The Factors of Anxiety	Numbers of Items	Total of items
Communication Apprehension	1, 9, 14, 18, 24, 27, 29, 32	8
Fear of Negative Evaluation	3, 7, 13, 15, 20, 23, 25,31, 33	9
Test Anxiety	2, 8, 10, 19, 21	5
Anxiety in Classroom	4, 5, 6, 11, 12, 16, 17, 22, 26, 28 30	11

Regarding the use of language learning strategies among participants, Oxford's Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) is adapted as questionnaire[11]. The questionnaire of SILL contains 34 items in six groups as the detailed below:

Table 2. Numbers of items in Language Learning Strategies questionnaire

Groups of Strategy	Numbers of Items	Total of items
Memory	1,2,3	3
Cognitive	4,5,6,7,8,9	6
Compensation	10,11,12,13,14,15,16	7
Metacognitive	17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26	10
Affective	27,28,29,30,31	5
Social	32,33,34	3

4.3 Participants

The FLCAS questionnaire was distributed to 108 students (45 males and 63 females) of Islamic State University Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang Indonesia studying at different disciplines that selected based on convenience sampling method. All these participants have taken the course of Intensive Arabic Learning Program that is obligatory for one year at the first study.

4.4 Data Analysis Method

In order to analysed the data, the descriptive statistics were used by performing the SPSS (version 21) in calculating means and standard deviation to determine the factors of anxiety in arabic learning as a foreign language and the use of language learning strategies among participants. In addition to this, Pearson product-moment correlation was also analysed by using SPSS in determining any statistically significant correlation among participants.

5. Result and Discussion

The first question was designed to determine levels of anxiety are present among university students. The results of descriptive statistics were illustrated below:

Table 3. Scores of Foreign Language Anxiety across gender

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Male	45	69.18	7.21	51	82
Female	63	75.40	7.05	55	89
Total	108	72.80	7.73	51	89

The table shows that total foreign language anxiety scores ranged between 51 and 89 with the total mean score of 72.80 (standar deviation=7.21). Regarding gender, foreign language anxiety scores for male ranged between 51 and 82 and for female from 55 to 89, which female students' mean (75.40) is higher than male students' mean (69.18). Based on the FLCAS, the means for anxiety classified into three levels: low anxiety (score ranged 33-66), average anxiety (score ranged 67-132), high anxiety (score ranged 133-165). Accordingly, the level total of foreign language anxiety is at average level. In terms of gender, both male and female, the mean scores are also at average level. The second question aimed to identify the types of language learning strategies that university students use. The mean score of six categories of SILL are reported in the table below:

Table 4. Mean score and standard deviation of Language Learning Strategies

Strategy Categories	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Minimum	Maximum
Memory	3.13	0.77	1.00	4.67
Cognitive	3.45	0.61	2.17	5.00
Compensation	3.57	0.71	2.14	5.00
Metacognitive	3.43	0.53	2.10	4.60
Affective	3.26	0.69	1.80	4.80
Social	3.37	0.70	2.00	4.67

As can be seen in table, all means fall between 3.26 and 3.57 on a scale of 1-5. The table reported that compensation as the most frequently used (mean=3.57), followed by cognitive (Mean=3.45), metacognitive (mean=3.43), social (mean=3.37), affective (mean=3.26), and memory strategies (mean=3.13). Based on Oxford's analysis of the SILL average, the means for strategy groups are classified into three levels namely High (3.5-5.0), Medium (2.5-3.4), and Low (1-2.4). According to the table below, only compensation strategy falls in the high level, while the other five strategy groups fall in the medium level.

Table 5. The rank of strategy categories

Rank	Strategy	Mean	Level
1	Compensation	3.57	High
2	Cognitive	3.45	Medium
3	Metacognitive	3.43	Medium
4	Social	3.37	Medium
5	Affective	3.26	Medium
6	Memory	3.13	Medium
	Overall	3.44	Medium

The third question that was stated in this study was: “Is there any significant relationship between foreign language anxiety and language learning strategies among university students?”, to answer this research question, pearson product-momen correlation was used.

Table 6. Correlation between foreign language anxiety and language learning strategies

		Anxiety	Strategies
Anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	-,190*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,049
	N	108	108
Strategies	Pearson Correlation	-,190*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,049	
	N	108	108

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The table illustrated that there is a negative correlation between foreign language anxiety and language learning strategies. However, the size of the correlation was not very high ($r=.190$, $p<0.05$, $n=108$)

Table 7. Correlation between level of Anxiety and different language learning strategies

		Memory	Cognitive	Compensation	Metacognitive	Affective	Social
Foreign language Anxiety	Pearson Correlation	-,271**	-,228*	-,221*	,124	,183	,037
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,005	,018	,022	,201	,058	,701
	N	108	108	108	108	108	108

**.. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

It can be seen in table, there is a significant negative correlation between foreign language anxiety and memory strategies ($r=-.271$) at the 0.05 level of significance. In addition, a negative correlation was found between cognitive ($r=-.228$) and compensation strategies ($r=-.221$) at the 0.01 level of significance. On the other hand, there is no significant on the other three strategy groups.

6. Discussion and conclusion

The first question in this research is to determine the levels of foreign language anxiety among university students. The results show that the total mean for the entire group of participants was computed to be 72.80, meaning that the overall students in this study experience foreign language anxiety at average level. Regarding gender, compared to male students (mean=69.18), female students (mean=75.40) tend to feel little more anxious while learning arabic language. This means that foreign language anxiety may be a major obstacle for many students taking arabic courses in maulana malik ibrahim islamic state university malang, Indonesia. The presence of

anxiety in learning Arabic as foreign language can be caused by many factors such as test-taking. The second research question is to find the frequency of language learning strategies applied by students taking arabic courses in Maulana Malik Ibrahim Islamic State University Malang, Indonesia. The results illustrate that participants used all strategy types ranging from medium to high level with the total mean score of 3.44 (medium level). Compensation strategies are the most frequently ($M=3.57$) used by students in learning Arabic as foreign language, followed by metacognitive strategies ($M=3.43$), social strategies ($M=3.37$), affective strategies ($M=3.26$), and memory strategies ($M=3.13$) as the lowest. These results support the findings of Phillips as stated in Mohammadi et. al. He found in his study that metacognitive strategies were the highest used by the participants, while memory strategies were the least.

The third research question is to discover the relationship between foreign language anxiety and language learning strategies in learning Arabic. The results show that there is a statistically negative correlation ($r=.190$, $p<0.05$, $n=108$) between FLA and LLS. This correlation means that the more students used all strategy categories in learning Arabic, the lower foreign language anxiety they will experience. The results of current study is in line with findings of Shabani [1] in Iranian students context. He found that the level of foreign language anxiety and the use of language learning strategies had a statistically significant correlation in a negative form, meaning the more students use language learning strategies, the less they feel anxious. In addition, the present results support the findings of Mohammadi et. al[17]. They found that high language learning strategies users had a relatively lower foreign language anxiety than low language learning strategies users.

In conclusion, based on the findings of this research the overall students taking Arabic courses feel foreign language anxiety in average level. In terms of the use of language learning strategies, they use all six strategies categories ranging from medium to high level. Finally, there is a statistically significant negative correlation between foreign language anxiety and language learning strategies in learning arabic among students taking Arabic courses in Maulana Malik Ibrahim Islamic State University Malang, Indonesia.

References

- [1] M. B. Shabani, "On the Relationship between Foreign Language Anxiety and Language Learning Strategies among Iranian EFL Learners," *Int. J. Educ. Investig.*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 9–23, 2015.
- [2] P. D. MacIntyre and R. C. Gardner, "The Subtle Effects of Language Anxiety on Cognitive Processing in the Second," *Language Learning*, vol. 44, no. 2. pp. 283–306, 1994.
- [3] R. Ellis, "Instructed Second Language Acquisition a Literature Review," *Book*. p. 58, 2005.
- [4] E. K. Horwitz, M. B. Horwitz, and J. Cope, "Foreign language classroom anxiety," *Mod. Lang. J.*, vol. 70, no. 2, pp. 125–132, 1986.
- [5] A. J. Onwuegbuzie and C. E. Daley, "Cognitive , and of Affective , Predictors Achievement Demographic Foreign-Language," *Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 94, no. 1. pp. 3–15, 2000.
- [6] Z. Na, "A Study of High School Students' English Learning Anxiety," *Asian EFL J.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 22–34, 2007.
- [7] E. K. Horwitz, "Language Anxiety and Achievement," *Annu. Rev. Appl. Linguistics*, vol. 21, pp. 112–126, 2001.
- [8] S. Abu-Rabia, "Teachers' role, learners' gender differences, and FL anxiety among

- seventh-grade students studying English as a foreign language,” *Educ. Psychology*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 711–721, 2004.
- [9] J. T. S. Wilson, “Anxiety in Learning English as a Foreign Language: Its Association with student variables, with overall proficiency, and with performance on an oral test,” Universidad de Granada, 2006.
- [10] M. O. Effiong, “Factors influencing foreign language classroom anxiety: an investigation of English learners in four Japanese universities,” 2013.
- [11] R. L. Oxford, “Language learning strategies: What every teacher should know,” in *Language Learning Strategies*, 1990.
- [12] A. D. Cohen, “Strategies in learning and using a second Language.” 1998.
- [13] J. M. O’Malley and A. U. Chamot, “Learning Strategies in Second Language Acquisition,” *Tesol Quarterly*, vol. 8, no. 2. pp. 129–136, 1990.
- [14] R. I. Lucas, “English Language Learning Anxiety among Foreign Language Learners in the Philippines,” *Philippine ESL Journal*, vol. 7, no. July. pp. 94–119, 2011.
- [15] R. Noormohamadi, “On the Relationship Between Language Learning Strategies and Foreign Language Anxiety Noormohamadi,” *Pan-Pacific Association of Applied Linguistics*, vol. 13, no. 1. pp. 39–52, 2009.
- [16] R. C. Gardner and P. D. MacIntyre, “A student’s contribution to second language learning: Part II, affective factors,” in *Language Teaching*, 1993, pp. 1–2.
- [17] E. G. Mohammadi, R. Biria, M. Koosha, and A. Shamsavari, “The Relationship between Foreign Language Anxiety and language Learning Strategies among University students,” *Theory Pract. Lang. Stud.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 637–646, 2013.

